

SPECIES COMPOSITION AND NUMBER OF INSECTS FOUND IN VEGETABLE, CUCURBIT FIELDS OF THE BUKHARA REGION

A.R. Rayimov, PhD, Doc., Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute.

ravimov78@bk.ru, ravimovavaz@buxdupi.uz

Abstract: In the research the diversity, abundance, distribution by biotopes and seasonal changes in the composition of insect species found in vegetable melon agrocenoses in Bukhara region are analyzed. The results of our study complement the resources in this area to some extent. The diversity of biotic, abiotic and anthropogenic factors certainly affects the fauna of insects. The intense changes in climatic conditions occurring in recent years, as well as alterations in the types of agricultural crops, will naturally affect the entomofauna of the Bukhara region. Updating the composition of agricultural crops in the country, introduction of new varieties and types of crops, in turn, contribute to an increase in the diversity of insects.

Keywords: insect, vegetable, melon, agrocenosis, arthropoda, diptera

Introduction. A comprehensive study of insects that are important in nature allows to manage their numbers and maintain environmental sustainability as well as insect diversity. Hence, special attention is being paid to environmental protection, biodiversity conservation and rational use of biological resources in our republic. The study of the current state of species composition, abundance, biotopic distribution, reproduction biology and ecology of insects across Bukhara region holds scientific and practical significance.

Material and methodology: Following data is analyzed on the basis of data obtained around Bukhara region between the years of 2015 and 2022. Our research was carried out in the fields of greenhouses, farms and fields of the Jondor, Romitan, Bukhara, Peshkin, Gijduvan, Shafirkan, Karvulbazar districts of the Bukhara region. The main attention was paid to the development of insects depending on the climatic conditions of the area during the seasons. The growing phase of crops in this territory falls on the first decade of March. But the real growing season of the main crops, including cultural ones, starts at the beginning of days with a soil temperature above $+10^{\circ}\text{C}$ on the territory. This period makes it possible to plant heat-loving plants, including vegetable melons. The materials were collected mainly from March to December, and partly in January and February. A number of industry determinants and scientific sources were used to determine the systematic position of insects. Online detectors were also used to identify species when needed [1,2,3,4,5,6]. Night calculations of routes were carried out using conventional LED lights. 120 counting works were done in various natural biotopes - semi-deserts, natural reservoirs, developed territories, agricultural landscapes and developed urban zones by stationary and route method, by counting, observation, sampling at different times of the year (spring, summer, autumn and winter). An entomological net handle with a diameter of 34-40 cm was used to collect insects. The collected samples were stored in plastic containers with 96% alcohol. Also, during the analysis of the materials of the article, entomological collections stored in the Bukhara State Zoological museum were used.

Result and discussion. Based on the analysis of the field material collected, it was found that the insects found in the agrocenoses of vegetable and cucurbits in Bukhara region belong to 8 orders (Orthoptera, dermaptera, Homoptera, thysanoptera, diptera, Coleoptera, lipidoptera, neuroptera) 3 subspecies (dolichocera, Brachycera, aphidinea) 16 families (gryllidae, gryllotalpidae, acrididae,

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labiduridae, labiidae, aphididae, Tephritidae, Thripidae, Scarabaeidae, Coccinellidae, Tenebrionoda, Meloidae, Chrysomelidae, Pieridae, Noctuidae, Chrysopidae) 31 species (Table 1).

Table 1

Species composition of insects found in vegetable-cucurbit agroecosystems of Bukhara region

S/n	Insect species	Vegetable field	Cucurbit crop field	Greenhouse
Kingdom. Metazoa				
Sub-kingdom. Eumetazoa				
Phylum. Arthropoda				
Sub-phylum Tracheata				
Class. Insecta				
Sub-class Ectognata				
Order. Orthoptera				
Sub-order. Dolichocera				
Family. Gryllidae				
1	Melanogryllus desertus	+	+	+
Family. Gryllotalpidae				
2	<i>Gryllotalpa gryllotalpa</i>	+	+	+
Sub-order. Brachycera				
Family. Acrididae				
3	<i>Truxalis nasuta</i>		+	
4	<i>Calliptamus italicus</i>	+	+	
5	<i>Dociostaurus marocanus</i>	+	+	
6	<i>Locusta migratoria</i>	+	+	
7	<i>Oedipoda caerulescens</i>	+		
8	<i>Thisioicetrinus pterostichus</i>	+		
Order. Dermaptera				
Family. Labiduridae				
9	Labidura riparia	+		

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Family. Labiidae			
10	<i>Labia minor</i>	+	+
Order. Homoptera			
Sub-order. Aphidinea			
Family. Aphididae			
11	<i>Aphis gossypii</i>	+	+
12	<i>Aphis medicaginis</i>		+
13	<i>Trifidaphis phascoli</i>	+	+
14	Myzodes persicae	+	
15	<i>Brevicoryne brassicae</i>	+	
16	Trialeurodes vaporariorum	+	+
Order. Diptera			
Family. Tephritid			
17	<i>Miopardalis pardalina</i>		+
Order. Thysanoptera			
Family. Thripidae			
18	<i>Thrips tabaci</i>	+	+
Order. Coleoptera			
Family. Scarabaeidae			
19	<i>Lethus rosmarus.</i>		+
20	<i>Polyphylla adspersa</i>	+	
21	<i>Oxythyrea cinctella</i>	+	+
Family. Coccinellidae			
22	<i>Ephilachna chysomelina</i>	+	+
23	<i>Cocimella septenpunctata</i>	+	+
Family. Tenebrionodae			
24	<i>Blaps halophile</i>		+

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Family. Meloida				
25	Mulabris guad ripunctata	+		
Family. Chrysomelidae				
26	Leptinotarsa desемlineata	+		+
Order. Lipidoptera				
Family. Pieridae				
27	<i>Pieris brassicae</i>	+		
28	<i>Pieris rapae</i>	+		
Family. Noctuidae				
29	Chloridea obsolete	+		
30	<i>Agrotis segetum</i>	+		
Order. Neuroptera				
Family. Chrysopidae				
31	Chrysopa carnea	+	+	+

The species found in almost all agrocenoses include chrysopa carnea, cocimella septenpunctata, thrips tabaci, trialeurodes vaporariorum, aphid gossypii, trifidaphis phascoli, gryllotalpa gryllotalpa, melanogryllus desertus (1. Table)

According to the taxonomic composition of insects found in vegetable and cucurbit crop agrocenoses of Bukhara region, the largest number of species (8 species) are representatives of the Coleoptera and Orthoptera orders and they consist of 25.8 % of the entomofauna. The families of Coleoptera (5,31,25%), the families of Orthoptera (3,18,75%) holds larger dominance compared to other representatives of the insects. This condition can also be explained by the fact that insects are rodents, the quantitative density of which is widespread in nature (Table 2).

Spectrum of orders and families of insects found in vegetable cucurbit agrocenoses of Bukhara.

Table 2

Order	Number of families	Share in relation to phytophages (%)	Number of species	Share in relation to phytophages (%)
Coleoptera	5	31.25	8	25.8
Orthoptera	3	18.75	8	25.8
Homoptera	1	6.25	6	19.35
Lipidoptera	2	12.50	4	12,9

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Diptera	1	6.25	1	3.22
Dermaptera	2	12.50	2	6.49
Thysanoptera	1	6.25	1	3,22
Neuroptera	1	6.25	1	3,22
Total	16	100	31	100

According to this pattern the Homoptera order occupies next place. They contain 6 species (19.35%) and 1 family-6.25%.

3.Table

Taxonomic composition of insects found in vegetable and cucurbit agrocenoses of Bukhara region

Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Species	
Arthropoda	Insecta	Orthoptera	Gryllidae	<i>Gryllus desertus</i>	
			Gryllotalpidae	<i>Gryllotalpa gryllotalpa</i>	
		Acrididae		<i>Truxalis nasuta</i>	
				<i>Calliptamus italicus</i>	
				<i>Dociostaurus marocanus</i>	
				<i>Locusta migratoria</i>	
				<i>Oedipoda miniata</i>	
				<i>Steuroides scalaris</i>	
		Dermaptera	Labiduridae	<i>Labidura riparia</i>	
			Labiidae	<i>Labia minor</i>	
		Homoptera	Aphididae		<i>Aphis gossypii</i>
					<i>Aphis medicaginis</i>
					<i>Trifidaphis phascoli</i>
					<i>Myzodes persicae</i>
	<i>Brevicoryne brassicae</i>				
	<i>Trialeurodes vaporariorum</i>				
Diptera	Tephritid	<i>Miopardalis pardalina</i>			
Thysanoptera	Thripidae	<i>Thrips tabaci</i>			

	Coleoptera	Scarabaeidae	<i>Lethus rosmarus.</i>	
			<i>Polyphylla adspersa</i>	
			<i>Oxythyrea cinctella</i>	
		Coccinellidae	<i>Ephilachna chysomelina</i>	
			<i>Cocimella septenpunctata</i>	
		Tenebrionodae	Blaps halophile	
		Meloida	Mulabris guad ripunctata	
		Chrysomelidae	Leptinotarsa desemlineata	
		Lipidoptera	Pieridae	<i>Pieris brassicae</i>
				<i>Pieris rapae</i>
Noctuidae	Chloridea obsolete			
	<i>Agrotis segetum</i>			
Neuroptera	Chrysopidae	Chrysopa carnea		

It is noticeable that there are a number of families according to species diversity. The presence of insects of 16 families was observed in vegetable and cucurbit agroecosystems. 11 families out of them include 1 species (Gryllidae, Gryllotalpidae, Labiduridae, Labiidae, Tephritidae, Thripidae, Tenebrionodae, Meloidae, Chrysomelidae, Noctuidae, Chrysopidae), make up 68.75% of the total number of families, and 3 families, including 2 species, make up 18.75% (Coccinellidae, Pieridae, Noctuidae), 1 family with 3 species makes up 6.25% (Scarabaeidae) 2 families with 6 species make up 12.5% (Aphididae, Acrididae) (3.Table).

In vegetable-cucurbit agroecosystems, the root of the plant is damaged by Gryllotalpidae, - agrotis segetum, aboveground organs-aphids, Noctuids, Trips, trialeurodes vaporariorum, and melon are damaged by the worm miopardalis pardalina.

Conclusion. Currently, the development and implementation of effective measures is possible only after determining the species composition of the pest fauna, which are an integral part of the biodiversity of vegetable and melon agroecosystems. The study of the fauna of insects found in vegetable, cucurbit agroecosystems of the Bukhara region, the creation of their cadastre, constant monitoring is important to protect the species of practical importance. It is also urgent to assess the state of insect populations found on vegetable and cucurbit fields of the Bukhara region by studying and identifying trends in their changes, developing recommendations on ways to preserve rare and endangered species. Also, by regularly conducting these studies, we receive information about changes in insect activity depending on the season of the year and, thus, increase our ability to control the number of insect pests of vegetable and cucurbit agroecosystems.

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